

A Schematic Model of Composite Particles beyond Standard Model*

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Abstract

The model of the Possible Composite particles that lies beyond standard model is discussed in this note. This note also attempts to suggest that quarks are however composite particles. The speculations made here must be identified experimentally in high energy accelerators.

Keywords: Hadrons, Fermions, Boson

The thorough study of cosmic rays in last centuries revealed several zoos of new exotic particles, which experimentalist recognized as a great achievement in particle physics. Few super exotic forms of physics still needs to be analyze and observe. Recently [1] it has been shown that possible spin not fermions and bosons exists based on such bizarre sequence we will propose that many composite particles exist with different quarks of specific composition. We will typically construct our model on spin criteria. Recall that hadrons typically baryons and mesons are composed of three valence quarks and quark - antiquark pairs respectively. Similar composition but different particles must exist. Models is described below

Analogy with baryons (B) = $q+q+q=1/2 + 1/2 - 1/2=1/2$ (assume proton)

And $1/2 + 1/2 + 1/2 = 3/2$ (already discovered)

Analogy with mesons (M) = $q + q^* = 1/2 - 1/2=0$

And $1/2 + 1/2 = 1$ (both are bosons)

Based on this analogies new models are as follows

Let the baryon like particle be A, $A=1/4+1/4-1/4=1/4$ (not fermions)

And $A=1/4+1/4+1/4=3/4$ (not fermions)

Let the meson like particle be B, $B=1/4-1/4=0$ (bosons)

And $B=1/4+1/4= 1/2$ (fermions).

Speculations can also be made that quarks are made up of different component particles. Few possibilities are explained and predicted

Possibility 1, $q=1/4+1/4=1/2$

Possibility 2, $q=1/2+0=1/2$

Possibility 3, $q=1/2+1/2-1/2=1/2$ (proton like model)

These ideas needs to be further developed and needs experimental measurements to finally conclude it.

References

[1] Deep Jyoti Dutta. (2018). Dynamical Pattern of Elementary Particles.
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